

CURRENT SCENARIO AND CHALLENGES IN FOOD PROCESSING INDUSTRY

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Abstract

Indian Food Processing Industry is the world's second-largest producer of food next to China and has the potential of being the biggest in the food and agriculture sector. The Indian food industry is poised for huge growth, increasing its contribution to world food trade every year. In India, the food sector has emerged as a high-growth and high-profit sector due to its immense potential for value addition, particularly within the food processing industry. Accounting for about 32 percent of the country's total food market, The Government of India has been instrumental in the growth and development of the food processing industry. The government through the Ministry of Food Processing Industries (MOFPI) is making all efforts to encourage investments in the business. It has approved proposals for joint ventures (JV), foreign collaborations, industrial licenses, and 100 percent export oriented units. The Indian Food Processing Industry with its vast potential has emerged as one of the major drivers of economic growth and development. India has been and is one of the world's major food producers but accounts for less than 1.5% of international food trade. This indicates vast scope for both investors and exporters. India's increased urbanization, improved standards of living and the convenient need of dual-income families point out to the major market potentialities in the food processing and market sectors. Being one of the world's largest producers of food grains, India has been ranked second in the world for the production of fruits and vegetables and regarded first in milk production providing much-needed food security to the nation.

Keywords : Collaborations , Industrial licenses, Immense potential, Investors, Urbanization.

1.Introduction

The Food processing industry is poised for huge growth, increasing its contribution to world food trade every year. In India, the food sector has emerged as a high-growth and high-profit sector due to its immense potential for value addition, particularly within the food processing industry. Accounting for about 32 per cent of the country's total food market, The Government of India has been instrumental in the growth and development of the food processing industry. The government through the Ministry of Food Processing Industries is making all efforts to encourage investments in the business. It has approved proposals for joint ventures (JV), foreign collaborations, industrial licenses, and 100 per cent export oriented units. Food processing is the transformation of cooked ingredients, by physical or chemical means into food, or of food into other forms. Food processing combines raw food ingredients to produce marketable food products that can be easily prepared and served by the consumer. As per Ministry of Food Processing of India (MOFPI), the term 'food processing'

is mainly defined as a process of value addition to the agricultural or horticultural produce by various methods like grading, sorting and packaging. In other words, it is a technique of manufacturing and preserving food substances in an effective manner with a view to enhance their shelf life; improve quality as well as make them functionally more useful. It covers a wide spectrum of products from sub- sectors comprising agriculture, horticulture, plantation, animal husbandry and fisheries. It also includes other industries that use agricultural inputs for manufacturing of edible products.

Accounting for about 32 per cent of the country's total food market, The Government of India has been instrumental in the growth and development of the food processing industry. The government through the Ministry of Food Processing Industries (MOFPI) is making all efforts to encourage investments in the business. India's food processing industry received 43% higher foreign direct investment (FDI) in the fiscal 2016-17 on the back of favourable policy measures. The food processing industry plays a vital role in the economy of any country because it links agriculture to industry. The food processing industry is responsible for diversification of agriculture, improvement of value-added opportunities, and creation of excess that can be exported. The food processing industry of India is one of the largest in the world in terms of manufacture, use, export, and development. The sector has immense potential to contribute to growth and employment opportunities of the country. The food processing industry in India has players from private, public and cooperative sectors. The Food Products Order (FPO) of 1955, Meat Food Products Order (MFPO) of 1973, and Food and Standards Act of 2006 ensure that the food items made after processing in India meet international standards of hygiene and quality.

2.Opportunities in Food Processing Industry

There are abundant opportunities for food processing companies in India. The demand for various products of food processing industry is on the rise because of the increase in per capita income of the Indians which results in higher spending on value added foods. In terms of volumes of production, India ranks amongst the highest in the world in some of the food products. The table below shows areas of Food Processing in India which have considerable output.

Table No-01

Food Processing Category	Amount Annually (in Tonnes)	Processed (in Million)	Rank in the world in terms of production
Milk and milk products	88		1st
Fruits and Vegetables	150		2nd
Rice	132		2nd
Sugarcane	289		2nd
Fish Production	6.3		3rd

Wheat, Groundnuts, Tea, Coffee, Spices, Sugar, Eggs and Oilseeds	-	Amongst the top five producers in the world
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This shows that a lot of supply is available for processing in India. The opportunity emerges when we analyze the percentage of volume that is processed to the volume that is produced. In India around 2% of fruits and vegetables are processed, 37% of milk is processed 1% of meat and poultry is processed and 12% of fish is processed. Comparing this to 80% quantity produced being processed in developed countries; we realize that a massive opportunity exists in the food processing business in India.

3.Reasons to invest in food industry

- 1) India ranked 12th in the World in exports of food and food products in 2017
- 2) Major industries constituting the food processing sector are grain milling, sugar, edible oils, beverages, fruits & vegetables processing and dairy products.
- 3) The contribution of the food processing sector to the Gross Value Addition (GVA) in 2014-15 amounts to USD 22 billion at 2011-12 prices. In 2016-17, GVA in food processing grew by 5.78%
- 4) Food processing industry is one of the major employment intensive segments contributing 11.69% of employment generated in all Registered Factory sector in 2017.

4.Issues/ Challenges of Food Processing Industry

- Indifference of policy makers as very little outlays are allocated in Five Year Plans. In the XI FYP, an outlay of Rs. 4000 crore was earmarked out of which significant proportion was not spent
- The legislation's like APMC Acts, Essential Commodities Act, etc restricts free movement of commodities
- Very poor infrastructure i.e. near absence of technologies, incubation facilities, pre-cooling chambers, irradiation facilities, etc
- High tariffs in the form of high excise duties as well as import duties
- Non-tariff barriers in the form of stringent regulation of laboratory testing, grading, sampling and packaging.
- Lack of entrepreneurship, as 70% of the total value of food processing items manufactured in India is dominated by the unorganized sector
- Lack of training facilities related to this industry
- Indian agriculture focuses on traditional crops rather than market-oriented agriculture with diversified commercial crops.

5.HR Challenges in the Food Processing Industry

1. Access to labour with the right skills and talent retention poses a big challenge in workforce management
2. Access to specialized employees in specialized fields like Food Science is difficult
3. Attracting talent is a challenge as employees do not see this industry as a job seeking opportunity
4. The industry is vulnerable to litigation by consumer groups and hence employee training on quality, food safety and compliance is critical
5. Generating Statutory Compliance and HR Reports of different locations.

6.10 Measures to ensure Food security

1. Education and literacy

Role of education in improving farm efficiency and technology adoption has been well established. As agriculture transformed from subsistence to commercial level, farmers seek information on a wide range of issues to acquire knowledge or upgrade their skills and entrepreneurial ability. Literacy emerges as an important source of growth in adoption of technology, and use of modern inputs like fertilizers and machines.

2. Crop diversification

Food availability is a necessary condition for food security. India is more or less self sufficient in cereals but has deficit in pulses and oilseeds. Due to changes in consumption patterns, demand for fruits, vegetables, dairy, meat, poultry, and fishery products has been increasing.

3. Tackling climate change

Food security in India can be achieved by paying higher attention to issues such as climate change, limiting global warming, including the promotion of climate-smart agricultural production systems and land use policies at a scale to help adapt and mitigate ill effects of climate change.

4. Integrated water management

India needs to produce more crop per unit of land and water resources. Improved management of irrigation water is essential in enhancing production and productivity, food security and poverty alleviation. Agriculture is the biggest user of water accounting for over 80 percent of the water withdrawals. It has been projected that availability of water for agriculture use in India may be reduced by 21 percent by 2020, resulting in drop of yields, especially rice, leading to price rise and threat to food security of the poor. Modern methods of irrigation like sprinkler, drip irrigation, fertigation, among other water efficient tools need to be adopted on larger scale.

5. Integrated nutrient management

Attention needs to be given to balanced use of nutrients. Phosphorus deficiency is the most wide spread soil fertility problem in both irrigated and non-irrigated rainfed areas. To improve the efficiency of fertilizer-use, what really needed is enhanced location-specific research on efficient fertilizer practices, improvement in soil testing services, development of improved fertilizer supply and distribution systems and development of physical and

institutional

infrastructure.

6. Improved varieties

In several regions, farmers are not able to get information about the availability of new and improved varieties and some are not having access to quality seeds of these varieties, resulting in lesser yields. This situation has to be corrected by developing a national-level network to monitor and coordinate the activities with the various State government functionaries working in the area of crop production.

7. Improved technology adoption

Adoption of technologies like integrated nutrient management, integrated pest management and integrated weed management need to be made available for adoption to ensure higher production and sustainability of production base.

8. Awareness on population growth

The awareness of the pressures of increasing population growth and consumption patterns on ecosystem functioning should be created to sensitize farmers on adoption of sustainable crop cultivation and management practices.

9. Focus on small farmers

Increase in food production in the country does not necessarily ensure food security, if the poor do not have the buying power. Therefore, participation of small farmers in food production is essential to achieve food security. Most of them being illiterate and having failed earlier either in adopting new technologies or repaying the loan provided under various development schemes. They need support not only to procure inputs but also to gain confidence.

10. Agricultural research education

The agricultural education in India is facing one of the biggest challenges. It has to identify its role in equipping the human resources for enhanced agricultural productivity and sustainable use of natural resources. Agricultural colleges and universities were initially assigned to disseminate scientific knowledge and skills to the farming community and to train them to use such skills for better output.

7. Conclusion

Food processing is typically a mechanical process that utilizes large mixing, grinding, chopping and emulsifying equipment in the production process. The food-processing sector is crucial for the India's development in the era of globalisation, to not only do well on the international front but also to achieve self adequacy on the domestic front. It establishes a vital link between agriculture and the consumer, hence ensuring the manifold growth of the economy. India is the world's second largest producer of food next to China and holds the potential to acquire the numero uno status with sustained efforts. The food processing process introduce a number of contamination risks. food processing include toxin removal, preservation, easing marketing and distribution tasks, and increasing food consistency. In addition, it increases yearly availability of many foods, enables transportation of delicate perishable foods across long distances and makes many kinds of foods safe to eat by deactivating spoilage and pathogenic micro-organisms. the future of the food processing industry is dazzling, with food safety, quality assurance and hygiene norms gaining

importance. The stringent rules laid by the government are sure to take this industry to global standards.

Though there are many promising dynamics which support good growth of food processing industry, there are still some significant constraints which, if not addressed sooner, can impede the growth prospects of the Food Processing Industry in India. One of the biggest constraints is that this industry is capital intensive. It creates a strong entry barrier and allows limited number of players to enter the market. Players mean competition which reduces efforts to improve quality standards. Major challenges faced by the Indian food processing industry include: educating consumers that processed foods can be more nutritious; dealing with low price elasticity for processed food products; need for distribution network; development of marketing channels; streamlining of food laws; improving food quality standards and strengthening food testing network; strengthening institutional framework to develop manpower for improving R&D capabilities to address global challenges. These challenges must be addressed to achieve full potential of the Indian food processing industry.

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